

Mössbauer and Infrared Spectroscopic Studies of Molecular Complexes of Oxine with Hexacyanoferrates[†]

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Oxine forms molecular adduct complexes with ferrocyanic and ferricyanic acids. Mössbauer spectra of both the complexes are of complex nature. These have been resolved into different sets of lines indicating the possibility of different iron sites. Inter-molecularly hydrogen bonded structures have been proposed. Infrared evidence also supports these conclusions.

STUDIES on disubstituted tetracyanoferrate(II) complexes with diamines, such as 2,2'-dipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline have been reported in literature¹. Saha and Saha² attempted to prepare similar complexes with 8-hydroxyquinoline(oxine) but instead ended up with the adduct type complexes with molecular compositions $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ Oxine and $K_3Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 2$ Oxine. Later, Pal and Manna³ reinvestigated these adducts and suggested one of the adducts to have molecular formula, $H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4Ox \cdot 3H_2O$ or $(OxH)_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 3H_2O$ on the basis of conductometric studies. We have prepared the adduct type complexes of ferro- and ferri-cyanic acids and carried out their Mössbauer and ir studies. Since, 8-hydroxyquinoline itself may be inter-molecularly hydrogen bonded, it could also involve itself with other such potential molecules where covalently bonded H atoms are available. Mössbauer spectroscopy has been widely used in the study of a variety of chemical bonding problems⁴⁻⁸. Earlier, studies of anhydrous ferro-, ferri-cyanic and nitroprussic acids by Mössbauer⁹⁻¹¹, infrared¹²⁻¹⁴ and refractometric¹⁵ studies have shown that these molecules are inter-molecularly hydrogen bonded⁴⁻⁸. Therefore, we thought it fit to investigate the possibility of three-dimensional hydrogen bonded structures for these molecular complexes.

Experimental

All reagents were of A.R. (B.D.H.), G.R. (S. Merck) or of high purity grade and used as such without further purification.

Preparation of complexes: The compounds were prepared by a method similar to that given by Pal and Manna³.

$H_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 4Oxine \cdot 3H_2O$: An aqueous solution of $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ (10 g) was mixed with oxine (6.86 g) dissolved in 5M acetic acid (37 ml). The

mixture was stirred well whence red-brown complex was formed. It was filtered, washed with distilled water and dried in vacuum over fused $CaCl_2$. Final colour was chocolate brown. Pal and Manna³ have determined its composition by conductometric titration. Its microanalytical data was in good agreement (Found: C, 58.85; H, 4.89; N, 16.15; Fe, 6.34. calcd. C, 59.30; H, 4.47; N, 16.47; Fe, 6.57%).

$H_3Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3Oxine \cdot 4H_2O$: Similar to above, an aqueous solution of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ (10 g) was mixed with oxine (8.8 g) in 5 M acetic acid (30 ml). The contents were stirred whence yellow coloured complex was formed. It was filtered, washed with water and dried in vacuum desiccator. No change in colour was observed (Found: C, 53.98; H, 4.24; N, 17.52; Fe, 7.15. calcd. C, 54.85; H, 4.43; N, 17.45; Fe, 7.76%).

The shining complexes are quite stable. The molecular composition of the ferricyanic acid adduct was further checked by conductometric titration as given below.

Conductometric titration: The conductometric titration was carried out to estimate the molecular composition of ferricyanic acid adduct. The solution containing about 50 mg of compound in 25 ml distilled water was titrated against NaOH solution (0.199 M) conductometrically on Metrohm E382 conductometer. Typical titration curve is given in Fig. 1 which yields an equivalent weight of 121.15. Assuming three oxine molecules, six protons will be available (three from ferricyanic acid and three from oxine molecules). Therefore, molecular weight of the adduct would be 726.9 which is comparable to the calculated value of 721.9 assuming the formula $H_3Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3Oxine \cdot 4H_2O$.

Mössbauer spectra: Mössbauer spectra at room temperature, were recorded on a ECIL MBS-35 constant velocity transducer drive Mössbauer spectrometer. A ~5 mCi ⁵⁷Co(Rh) source obtained

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Fig. 1. Conductometric titration curve for ferricyanic acid adduct of oxine; NaOH=0.199 N, amount of adduct =51.94 mg.

from Amersham International (U.K.) was used. Natural iron foil (25 μm) was used for calibration while sodium nitroprusside (SNP) was used for standardisation. All isomer shifts reported here have been converted with respect to SNP. The spectral lines were fitted visually assuming Lorentzian line shape.

Ir and magnetic measurements: Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on Specord 75 ir spectrophotometer in the range 4000-400 cm^{-1} . Magnetic moments were calculated from magnetic susceptibility measurements using Gouy balance method and $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as standard.

Results and Discussion

The characteristic ir frequencies for oxine and its molecular complexes with their most probable assignments are given in Table 1. The adduct $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{Ox} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is found to be diamagnetic with corrected molar susceptibility $11.4 \times 10^{-6}/\text{g}$ atom which is comparable to that reported by Saha and Saha³. The slight difference in values might be due to incorrect composition assumed by these

workers. The ferricyanic acid adduct gave $\mu_{\text{eff}}=2.49$ B.M. which is a little higher than that for one unpaired electron. However, it is still indicative of Fe^{III} low-spin state.

The Mössbauer spectrum of ferrocyanic acid adduct shown in Fig. 2 consists of three lines (1,2,3) with large line widths and unequal heights. It has been resolved into two sets of doublets (2',2 and 3',3) indicating two states or sites of iron. For the first set of doublet (2',2), Mössbauer parameters

Fig. 2. Mössbauer spectrum of $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{Ox} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

are $\delta=0.14 \pm 0.01$ mms^{-1} and $\Delta E_Q=0.35 \pm 0.04$ mms^{-1} with linewidths $\Gamma_{2'}=\Gamma_2=0.28$ mms^{-1} . Calculated parameters for the second set (3',3) are $\delta=0.32$ mms^{-1} and $\Delta E_Q=0.65 \pm 0.08$ mms^{-1} with line widths $\Gamma_{3'}=\Gamma_3=0.35$ mms^{-1} . δ values for both the sets are comparable to that for ferrocyanide indicating Fe^{II} in low-spin states^{5,6}. Thus ferrocyanide unit $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ seems to remain undisturbed by the outer oxine and water molecules. However, these may be bonded differently. For (2',2), δ value is similar^{9,16} to that for $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ although its ΔE_Q value is somewhat higher. Therefore, hydrogen bonded model similar to that in $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ may be possible where oxine molecules

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTIC IR FREQUENCIES OF OXINE AND ITS MOLECULAR COMPLEXES WITH FERROCYANIC AND FERRICYANIC ACIDS

Assignment	Oxine cm^{-1}	$\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{Ox} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ cm^{-1}	$\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{Ox} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ cm^{-1}
$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{C}}$	—	480 w	480 w
$\delta_{\text{Fe}-\text{CN}}$	—	530 vw, 570 m	530 w, 570 vw
$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}(\text{H})}$	1160 w	1080 m	1090 m
$\delta_{\text{O}-\text{H}(\text{Ph})}$	1270 m	1280 m	1300 m
$\delta_{\text{O}-\text{H}}$	—	1580 w	1590 m
$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}(\text{ring})$	1550 w	1540 w	1550 w
$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$	—	2010 b	2110 b
$\nu_{\text{OH}(\text{H}_2\text{O})}$	—	3500 vb	3500 vb
Other peaks	700, 740, 770	740, 800	740, 810

vw=Very weak, w=weak, m=medium, b=broad, vb=very broad.

are bonded through H(OH end). A three-dimensional model is proposed as shown in Fig. 3A. Large size of oxine molecules instead of H may explain higher ΔE_Q value. For set of lines (3',3) both parameters have higher values. Accordingly another hydrogen bonded structure is suggested (Fig. 3B), where two oxine molecules are bonded differently than the other two. Such type of structure is likely to cause large distortion in the octahedral geometry and hence a higher ΔE_Q value. Slightly higher δ value may be explained by assuming withdrawl of charge by H from central Fe via CN groups.

Fig. 3. Mössbauer spectrum of $H_2Fe(ON)_6 \cdot 3Ox \cdot 4H_2O$.

The Mössbauer spectrum of $H_2Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3Ox \cdot 4H_2O$ shown in Fig. 4 consists of two asymmetric lines and has been resolved into a singlet (1) and a

Fig. 4. Hydrogen bonded models for the oxine adduct of ferrocyanic acid, $H_2Fe(ON)_6 \cdot 4Ox \cdot 3H_2O$.

doublet (2',2). The singlet gave $\delta = 0.02 \pm 0.01$ mms⁻¹ with $\Gamma = 0.50$ mms⁻¹, and the doublet gave $\delta = 0.44 \pm 0.02$ mms⁻¹ and $\Delta E_Q = 0.52 \pm 0.06$ mms⁻¹ with linewidths $\Gamma_{2'} = \Gamma_2 = 0.40$ mms⁻¹. Both δ values are indicative of Fe^{III} low-spin state in octahedral geometry but in different sites. Since both δ values are comparable to that for other ferricyanides^{8,9}, it is presumed that $[Fe(CN)_6]^{3-}$ unit remains grossly unaffected. Like the former case there might be two iron sites out of which one may have somewhat symmetric environment resulting in a singlet and the other may correspond to distorted octahedron giving a doublet (2',2). The two possibilities are illustrated in Fig. 5A and B. In the former case, three oxine molecules may be involved in intermolecular unsymmetrical hydrogen bonding through

Fig. 5. Hydrogen bonded models for the oxine adduct of ferricyanic acid, $H_2Fe(ON)_6 \cdot 3Ox \cdot 4H_2O$.

both H atoms (one of OH and another of protonated to N) which results in a chelated type of structure. Normally it should have also given rise to quadrupole doublet but because of complex nature of spectra we have not been able to resolve it. This is evident from the higher linewidth of singlet. In the second case higher δ value may be explained in terms of π -electron charge withdrawn by oxine molecules from the metal by induction through H atoms.

Infrared spectra of the two adducts show all the characteristic vibrational and bending frequencies^{17,18}. Vibrational frequency due to C=N (ring) in the oxine molecule is observed at 1550 cm⁻¹ in all the three compounds, viz. oxine and its two adducts¹⁹. However, ν_{C-O} is shifted by ~ 80 cm⁻¹ and may be attributed to its possible participation in bonding with $H_2Fe(CN)_6$ and $H_2Fe(CN)_6$. The ν_{Fe-C} and δ_{Fe-CN} bands with weak intensities have been observed at 480 and

530 cm^{-1} , respectively. $\nu_{\text{Fe}-\text{C}}$ is lowered as compared to anhydrous acids. $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ band appears at 2010 and 2110 cm^{-1} , respectively for ferro- and ferri-cyanic acid adducts. No splitting was observed for this band. Further, these frequencies are lowered and raised when compared with CN stretching frequency for the respective anhydrous acids. Therefore, its spectral characteristics support our presumption that oxine is involved in weak bonding with N end of ferro- and ferri-cyanic acids, most probably through OH groups.

Conclusion: Oxine forms molecular complexes with $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ with molecular composition $\text{H}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 4\text{Ox} \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6 \cdot 3\text{Ox} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is suggested that protonated oxine molecules are involved in unsymmetrical hydrogen bonding yielding molecular species and three-dimensional hydrogen bonded structures.

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